

Strategic Alliances for New Product Development – Critical Perspective - Amandeep Midha, EMBA 2009, SBS Swiss Business School

The fast growing highly competitive and rapidly changing business environment, thus causes shorter product development and maturity cycles, and one expects to see advertisements in leading financial papers reading:

'Large Well-heeled Company with established distribution channels and aging product line seeks small, entrepreneurial, cash-starved technology leader with hot new product. Photos available upon request'

(Citation Referenced from "Crossing the Chasm" by Geoffrey A. Moore)

In business and engineering, new product development (NPD) is the term used to describe the complete process of bringing a new product or service to market. There are two parallel paths involved in the NPD process: one involves the idea generation, product design, and detail engineering; the other involves market research and marketing analysis. The companies typically see new product development as the first stage in generating and commercializing new products within the overall strategic process of product lifecycle

From high-tech industry perspective, Strategic alliances are claimed to be used by firms to acquire the complementary assets needed to develop products. The number of output of new products over a certain period depends on the number of alliances the firm enters into. However, the firm's capability to manage strategic alliances and the benefits from them are significantly dependent on the number of alliances at some point.

Logically speaking, the Law of Diminishing Returns should acts in disfavour for individual high tech firms participating in strategic alliance for new product development as it might cause forced obsolescence of their products in individual portfolio and could cannibalize that market entirely. Yet the trend does not seem to favour this rationale at all.

Pursuing new product development within an alliance has risen in popularity despite the difficulties encountered when trying to implement such an approach. These difficulties arise because managing new product development within an alliance is inherently complex. Partners tend to have difficulty in valuing resource contributions, protecting confidential technical information, creating a social network among new product development participants, maintaining a balance of power and preventing cannibalization of their firm's products by the jointly developed products.

A Chinese proverb says: 同床异梦 (tóngchuáng yì mèng), which means "To sleep in the same bed but having different dreams". The same might apply if the numbers of failed cases of new product development via strategic alliances are analyzed globally.

Thus, these fashionable arrangements appear to be liable to breakdown. The problem is that the sharing, obvious to both parties when embarked on the alliance, is never quite so clear once the activity becomes a routine. One partner's contribution is expected to be marketing, but the other partner may well have an ambitious marketing department which will not be sidetracked; at the same time one partner may have agreed to contribute the technical knowledge but is unwilling for the other partner to have the access to patents and other specialized knowledge anticipated when the agreement was put in practice.

Fig 1: Decision Flow towards Strategic Alliance based on my VRIO based considerations

Ideally, a new product development involves the following phases:

1. Idea Generation (also called Fuzzy Front End)
2. Idea Screening
3. Concept Development & Proofing
4. Business Analysis & First Evaluation
5. Beta Testing & Market Testing
6. Technical Implementation
7. Commercialization

Apart from these there are few additional factors favouring the Case of Strategic Alliances:

Faster Time to Market:

Product Companies also face the pressure of faster Time to Market (TTM) pressures which we have not considered so far in above discussion. To achieve reduce TTM objectives, companies often try to complete many of above 7 steps simultaneously and if done in Strategic Alliance fashion with competent skilled alliance partner, the TTM cycle time could be shorter than plain arithmetic reduction by factor of two. Thus, not only the mitigation of all the risks listed prior, but the 'greed' of generating revenues faster than anticipated earlier, acts as a carrot.

Reduction in Pressure from Competitive Forces:

There are significant all round cost savings arising out of such a marriage without which these forces would have acted against each other

Ease of Standardization:

Furthermore, in case of high tech industry, an alliance is among the equals attaches higher probability of success of 'standardization' once the product launch is over and reasonably successful. Such standardization and industry acceptance helps both the strategic partners to have much bigger footprint than either of them could have done individually.

These three factors favour the strategic alliances to great extent and tend to prove $1 + 1 > 2$ by just exploiting the best among both and projecting an idealistic win-win situation. By framing this utopia, two product managers sitting together might even start visualizing steps to include others in the form of 'consortium' (higher scale of alliance with multitude of corporations forming an alliance); but then the reality strikes!

As a rule, however, these types of alliances do better in boardroom than on the street. To start with, the company cultures are normally too antithetical with each other. A good example from publishing industry here is between Times of India group and Hindustan Times in their strategic alliance to co-produce the newspaper 'Mint' in collaboration with Wall-Street Journal. Historically, both groups have set exemplary rivalry and their staffs are always in run to outsmart the staff from other media group. The co-production of 'Mint' required them to act as jointly equal active partner of WSJ, mostly deploying their own personnel. But rivalry DNA prevalent among staff

prevented the co-production till the point the staff were removed from temporary deputation status from their original employers and relocated to a far off place to co-host the separate facility. Such incidents cause enormous frustration among entrepreneurs and managements.

To make matters worse, each side has possibly misrepresented itself one way or other during the negotiations, such that there is plenty of ammunition to fire at the other once the temper gets hot. This is particularly likely to be case when the entrepreneurs have been using acquisitions as essentially a financial exit strategy.

Another growing area of concern is 'Partner Opportunism' & 'Internationalized IPR Infringements' and possibility increase if one of the partners tries to take advantage of the technology sharing. The Quality Brand Protection Committee (QBMC) of China reports that counterfeits now operate at International Trade Fairs, directly competing with legitimate competitors by soliciting the sales from international trading companies.

A common complaint about co-created product development is couched in the terms such as: "We put in all the resources, but the partner takes half of the revenue." Safeguards against that perception are needed during the preparatory work as well as the wording of the final contract

Risks Involved in New Product Development:

The area of new product development is extremely challenging and keeps its entire set of stakeholders at their toes. Let's look into the details of the risks involved in the new product development activity taken up by a company X:

- Inaccurate Budgeting
- Design Flaws
- Failure by Outside Suppliers
- Missed Opportunities for Cooperation with outside Specialists
- Poorly coordinated development staff while focussing on other products
- Inaccurate Market and Technical Research findings
- Inadequately Durable Materials and Resources
- Loss of Critical Product Information to Competition
- Unforeseen Customer Rejection caused due to lack of proper trials
- Ineffective Leadership & Management Focus

However, strategic alliances come into picture not just to mitigate above risks alone and are of great interest to the decision makers. All good things begin with a thought/ignite in mind and that's where strategic alliances constitute themselves as catalyst to bring that thought into motion. Of course, some strategic alliances have been extremely successful. The alliance between Microsoft and Intel, what some have called the Wintel duopoly till today orchestrates the PC industry. Such alliances have been hugely powerful and moved mountains of market cap. Powerful as these relationships could be, the complexities of developing and maintaining such alliances are enough to daunt all.

Size Disparities

While it may not be always possible to match the size, hence the organizations need to prepare themselves in disparate partner mode as well. Both entrepreneurial ventures and established firms use cooperative strategies to innovate. An entrepreneurial venture, for example, may seek investment capital as well as firm's established distribution capabilities to successfully introduce one of its innovative products to the market. The parallel benefit for it could be the transfer of tacit knowledge to it from its established partner.

Alternatively, as the starting example in this paper, more established companies may need new technological knowledge and can gain access to it by forming alliances with smaller firms. Knowledge from these alliances helps firms to develop new capabilities. The ideal alliance is one in which the firms have complementary skills as well as compatible strategic goals.

However, when the size disparity is huge and established entity is desperate to add more products to its portfolio, it is common to see the larger entity using arm twisting tactics to turn it towards buyout or a merger. It is common to see many open-source software vendors finally turning themselves to an established player earlier in the form of shared platform or services (it brings ease of standardization benefit and labour cost savings) and later in the absence of its own management control, it offers itself as co-product of the product line offered by the established firm which takes over the product lifecycle control finally.

Ideas for Overcoming Typical Causes of Disputes in Strategic Alliances

1. Steering Group – The members of the steering group should be sufficiently senior and with enough clout to sort out problems
2. Policy Setting - The Steering group must have the power to make or implement policies which both parties will consider binding
3. Performance Appraisal – The steering group must appraise the performance of the alliance with the same strictness as it is required of any other activity of each firm
4. Contracts - Contracts are essential to cover an issue over which disputes are likely to arise. The contract needs to put an arbitrator in case of a failure to agree
5. Scale of Operations – needs to be determined beforehand and enshrined in the contracts
6. Who does what? This needs to be stipulated in the contract.
7. Firm's Commitment for Long Term - A Critical eye on the alliance partner firm's stock price movements, insider trading, and shareholding patterns to determine the commitment and degree of urgency and dependency towards the products developed via strategic alliance

Readiness for Marriage

Well, if there is Product Company ABC Inc. which has pioneered many products, is reasonably placed. The 'crossing of chasm' has successfully taken place for few of its products and enjoys the reputation of 'pioneer' and delivering comprehensive solutions in form of its products. Does that mean it will be the best match for any equal or larger sized product 'thinker' for a strategic alliance for new product development?

If ABC Inc. was the positioning for a pharmaceutical company where IPR sensitivity is most, it would have no choice rather than going alone or via contractual alliance, funding the research through various debts and spend its money and manpower through the complete NPD

However, if it was a high tech product company operating in fast cycle market, may be then an alliance would have been beneficial. The key question now is "Is it ready for marriage?"

As we see in many product companies, many companies do not have a 'design manager' as such. They employ consultants briefed to update those designs. A product manager incorporates these designs, does some prototyping, and passes them for development, hopefully with success.

Nowadays when the definitions of product and services are converging fast, the stress is on the need for each project to be tailor-made. Design focuses on market – as the market changes, so should the design. Arguably design belongs to marketing than to production, moving away from concentrating on what worked yesterday to what will sell tomorrow.

Hence, unless the company is "product-design-led" and the marketing staff demand considerable influence, it would have great risk of losing its focus in the new product development done via an alliance. This, not only could sabotage its alliance project success, but also its core operations as well.

Indian Perspective & Final Note:

New Product Development is extremely challenging and risky venture. Not many firms invest in them unless they are absolutely sure about its success. By the time, absolute surety is reached; multiple similar products are already in market in hands of early adopters and few of them even with early majority. An interesting analogy can be drawn from the Indian Software Industry where less than fraction percentage of them have R&D budget exceeding 3% of their gross annual revenues.

These 'dumb' IT majors of India firms who have thrived on inexpensive service revenues face the risk of being either stuck at end of value chain forever, or complete loss of business once cheaper alternative emerge.

For sure, Infosys till today has not taken the risk of conceptualizing or developing a product on its own going by market research done by itself or its experience. Wipro has little product development experience, but it sees increasing consumer durable business growth as better way to reward its shareholders.

If such is the stigma attached to new product development, even if wisdom strikes to these Indian IT majors one fine day; it is evident that they are not going to do it alone. Thus, the importances of strategic alliance come to foreground since the stakes are very high.

Interestingly, from the industry domain and operational style perspective, these IT majors look idempotent to each other when analyzed using VRIO (Value, Rarity, Imitability, and Organization) framework. Then, does it make sense for them to co-develop a new product at all?

Conclusion

New product planning & development should be first aligned to an individual company's strategy to achieve growth. These new planning and alliance structures need to be integrated with participating organization's processes to optimize corporate growth through these alliance-seeking opportunities.

After that, drawing a new product doughnut diagram would do the rest. Once the areas of attention and concern are identified, it would be much easier for the firm to decide the basis of strategic alliance and WIIFM (What's in it for me) benefit.

Once the alliance has been entered, continuous assessment of progress and review against the alliance objectives need to be done on continuous basis. It is common to see that the organizations today are acting in greed to develop a product to target a large market in great hurry and they are willing to sacrifice part of its earnings to its alliance partners. Plus, they enter many such alliances with multiple developments targeted at different market segments across multiple geographies. They must not forget that alliances are just the 'means', not the 'destination' for them to exist and thrive. Their shareholders want to remind them to do it alone 'next time' and succeed like no other before.

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